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An immune receptor activated in lung metastasis, Igsf9b, that facilitates immune evasion.

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Igsf9b functioned in concert with *PRRT* and *LRR16B* in execution of its role in immune tolerance. A second IGSF receptor, *Igsf21* functioned together with Igsf9b at sites marked by *Fam57b* and a second LRR family receptor, *RLTPR*.